

THE ROLE OF USING GAME TECHNOLOGY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *This article describes the process of influence of game technology on changing students' motivation. The introduction of game technologies in the teaching of the English language helps to increase the interest of students in learning science and to build their competence. It is important to use game technology in English lessons in the educational process because games encourage students to learn a foreign language and affect all aspects of their development: emotions, mind, will and behavior.*

Keywords: *foreign languages, game technology, teaching methods, role play, motivation, interactive games, didactic games, the purpose of the game, the task of the game.*

РОЛЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИГРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье описывается процесс влияния игровых технологий на изменение мотивации студентов. Внедрение игровых технологий в преподавание английского языка способствует повышению интереса учащихся к изучению науки и формированию их компетентности. Важно использовать игровые технологии на уроках английского языка в образовательном процессе, поскольку игры стимулируют учащихся к изучению иностранного языка и влияют на все стороны их развития: эмоции, разум, волю и поведение.*

Ключевые слова: *иностраннные языки, игровые технологии, методы обучения, ролевая игра, мотивация, интерактивные игры, дидактические игры, цель игры, задача игры.*

Introduction

Today, teaching through interactive games is becoming a tradition in the educational system. It is known that the lesson is conducted on the basis of various games, which ensures that students demonstrate their capabilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity rely on the fundamental needs of a person to express himself, find a stable place in life, self-control, and realize his potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Educational games should be based on educational subjects.

In the process of games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a regular lesson and works freely. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a method of teaching. Pupils participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, and the teacher also provides education to the pupil through them. The student believes that he can speak, listen, understand, and write in English while playing games, he is interested. Experience shows that in any game, regardless of the skill and age of the participants, they fall into an awkward situation. Therefore, the following pedagogical and psychological issues should be resolved before applying the game to educational practice. Every student should know the following while preparing for the game:

- the goal of the game;
- the task of the game;
- what topic the game is related to in the plan;
- to be able to use the skills and abilities formed in previous games in the next games.

It is known that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach independent thinking.

Taking into account the above characteristics, if the teacher explains or organizes the topic during the lesson with the students during the lesson, prepares role plays, and explains or organizes the topic, it creates a significant result and the motivation of the student to learn the language is formed. Below we will consider some of the didactic games and pedagogical technologies that we can use in the lessons to organize such a meaningful lesson:

"Creative problem solving". To use this method, the beginning of the story is read, and how it ends is referred to the judgment of the students;

Who is faster? The goal of the game is to develop the writing technique. The course of the game: the listeners are given cards with sentences written on them, and the words of the sentences on the card are arranged in order. The student who writes first and correctly will be the winner. This game is more effective in higher classes.

Who I am? - The goal of the game is to develop speaking techniques. The course of the game: a student in the group describes something or a person without naming it, and the rest of the students have to find who or what it is according to the description. This game improves verbal literacy. This game is more typical for primary classes.

Continued story - The goal of the game is to develop vocabulary. The course of the game: the class is divided into 2 groups and 2 types of stories are given in a semi-finished state, and the groups continue the story based on their fantasy and bring it to the end. The group that uses more new words is the winner. This game teaches students to work in harmony with each other. This game works better in higher grades.

Noisy dictation - The purpose of the game is to develop grammar. The course of the game: Students in the class are placed facing each other and must be able to correctly write down the words of the student in front of them while listening to each other at the same time. This game will be a little noisy and it is this noise that will allow them to develop word recognition even in such a situation. It improves listening skills. In English, words are not written as they are heard, for example, in the word speak, the diphthong {ea} gives the sound [i] and its transcription is [spi:k]. If the student can understand the words correctly, then this is a good result. This game is used in elementary and high school.

"Merry Riddles". Teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English. They learn unfamiliar words and find answers to riddles.

"Pantomime". In this, the teacher tells the students a word and the student show it. The rest of the students will have to find the word and say its name in English.

"Quick response". This type of game helps to improve the effectiveness of the lesson.

"Warm-up exercises". Using various games in the classroom to interest students in the lesson;

"A chain story" method helps to improve students' oral speech and strengthen memory;

"Acting characters" method can be used in all types of lessons. In order to teach the profession, people in professions such as "Interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the class and talk with students;

"Thinkers meeting" poets and writers such as U. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be "invited". At such a time, using the wise words they said in the lesson will help young people to be educated as perfect people;

The "When pictures speak" method is very convenient and helps to teach English and develop the oral speech of students, for this it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic;

"Quiz cards" cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time.

Last Man Standing. This game is a quick game. But it gives the students some time to think. This game encourages cooperative learning, that is, while other students are talking, the rest of the students are thinking of words themselves. You need a ball to play the game. And all students should stand in a circle. You need to choose a topic. For example: Things found in a kitchen, food, profession, etc. The game starts by throwing the ball to a student. That student says an English word about the topic and throws the ball to the next student. Each student who receives the ball will have to say something about this topic. If they repeat the words they were told or cannot find the words within a few seconds, they leave the game and watch the game sitting down. The main thing is that students who leave the game will still learn something.

Game technology is the most effective way to learn a foreign language. Game technology helps to organize students' speaking skills, as well as to teach and activate monologic and dialogic speech. Every teacher has many tools that help make learning a foreign language interesting and fascinating, because the teacher needs to arouse students' interest in the material being studied in the process of teaching a foreign language.

The role of game technology is to use it in different ways. Role-playing games often attract the student's attention, because such technologies enliven the lesson, increase the student's interest in the language being studied. In addition, a well-organized game creates conditions for the real use of a foreign language in the classroom. We can distinguish the following stages in the preparation of a role-playing game:

- determining the purpose and language material;
- creating a script for the game;
- distribution of roles in the game;
- psychological preparation of listeners.

When using role-playing games, the foreign language teacher must be aware that the game does not always go as planned. So, the success of the game depends on both the students and the teacher.

The educational influence of teachers is important for the emergence of game activity. Play is an integral activity in which all forms of human activity manifest themselves. That is, during the game, the student uses both intellectual and creative thinking skills. Mental and psychological structures corresponding to communicative, compensatory, healing, adaptation, strategic tasks are also formed in the game. There are games suitable for each student's level. The game forms the basis of social behavior, moral, aesthetic, ethical principles of the student's future personality. In the game, the student should express himself, because the game is the main means

of physical, spiritual and mental development. Game technology occupies a special place in the educational process.

It is very important that the teacher motivates the students and compares their progress with previous results. Then the students become interested in the language, and the desire to participate in the next game increases as a result of the same technology. Not every participant can participate equally in the game. It is very important to assign roles taking into account the individual characteristics of each student. For example, stronger students can be assigned the role of active characters, while shy students can take a passive role or be given a specific task. In this case, the teacher should single out the best player, write down the student's foreign language mistakes in the game, and correct their shortcomings at the end of the game. Obviously, all students in the group should participate in this process, because all students in the group should learn to communicate in a foreign language. Always remember that everyone is equal in the game.

Conclusion

Summarizing the above, it can be concluded that the role of games and game technologies used in English language classes is important. The game technique gives a practical direction to the learning process, which helps to maintain students' motivation to learn a foreign language. The need for play and the desire to play must be properly used and directed to solve specific problems in the educational process. The game, if it is involved in the entire pedagogical process, becomes a means of education and training. When the teacher conducts the game and organizes the student's interests in the game, it affects all aspects of the student's development: feeling, consciousness, will and behavior.

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